

Environmental and economic assessment of large-scale hydrogen supply chains across Europe: LOHC vs other hydrogen technologies

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Comprehensive assessment of LOHC vs. CGH_2 , LH_2 and LNH_3 hydrogen supply chains.
- Novel evaluation of the LOHC system H0-BT/H12-BT for large-scale hydrogen transport.
- Dehydrogenation identified as the key challenge for LOHC environmental performance.
- Land distribution is highly influenced by economies of scale.
- Repurposed pipelines considerably reduce costs for land distribution.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The transition to decarbonized energy systems positions hydrogen as a critical vector for achieving climate neutrality, yet its large-scale transportation and storage remain key challenges. This study presents a comprehensive life cycle assessment (LCA) and economic analysis of large-scale H_2 supply chains, evaluating the liquid organic hydrogen carrier (LOHC) system based on benzyltoluene/perhydro-benzyltoluene (H0-BT/H12-BT) against conventional technologies: compressed gaseous hydrogen (CGH_2), liquid hydrogen (LH_2) and liquid ammonia (LNH_3). The analysis includes multiple H_2 transportation scenarios across Europe, considering the steps: conditioning, sea transportation, post-processing and land distribution by truck or pipeline. Environmentally, LOHC currently faces higher environmental impacts than CGH_2 , driven by energy-intensive dehydrogenation process. Truck-based distribution further amplifies impacts, particularly over long distances, while pipeline-based distribution significantly reduces the environmental burdens where infrastructure exists. Sensitivity analysis reveals that using H_2 for dehydrogenation heat lowers process-level impacts but increases overall

Abbreviations: CAPEX, Capital expenditure; CEPCI, Chemical engineering plant cost index; CGH_2 , Compressed gaseous hydrogen; CO_2 , Carbon dioxide; DWT, Deadweight tonnage; EF, Environmental footprint; FU, Functional unit; GWP, Global warming potential; H0-BT/H12-BT, Benzyltoluene/Perhydro-benzyltoluene; H0-DBT/H18-DBT, Dibenzyltoluene/Perhydro-dibenzyltoluene; H_2 , Hydrogen; LCA, Life cycle assessment; LCC, Life cycle costing; LCI, Life cycle inventory; LCIA, Life cycle impact assessment; LCOH, Levelized cost of hydrogen; LH_2 , Liquefied hydrogen; LNH_3 , Liquid ammonia; LOHC, Liquid organic hydrogen carrier; MEGC, Multi Element Gas Containers; NO_x , Nitrogen oxides; NZE, Net Zero Emissions; OPEX, Operating expenditure; O_3 , Ozone; PGM, Platinum group metal; Pt, Platinum; SMR, Steam methane reforming; SO_2 , Sulfur dioxide; TOL/MCH, Toluene/Methylcyclohexane; TOTEX, Total expenditure; tpd, Tons per day; VOCs, Volatile organic compounds.

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supply chain impacts, questioning its net environmental benefit. Economically, LOHC remains competitive despite high dehydrogenation costs, benefiting from low sea transportation expenses, compatibility with existing fossil fuel infrastructure and potential for future CAPEX and OPEX improvements. While CGH₂ outperforms LH₂ and LNH₃, avoiding energy-intensive liquefaction and cracking, its storage requirements add considerable costs. For land distribution, LOHC trucks are optimal at lower capacities, whereas repurposed natural gas pipelines favour CGH₂ at higher scale, reducing costs by up to 84 %. Despite current trade-offs, the scalability, flexibility and synergies with existing infrastructure position LOHC as a promising solution for long-distance H₂ transport, contingent on technological maturation to mitigate dehydrogenation impacts.

1. Introduction

The global transition towards a sustainable energy system is essential to mitigate climate change and secure future energy needs without compromising environmental integrity. The Paris Agreement aims to limit global warming to well below 2 °C, preferably 1.5 °C, compared to pre-industrial levels, by urging a shift from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources [1]. Achieving this goal requires not only decarbonizing energy production but also overhauling the entire energy infrastructure to ensure its reliability and resilience. The Net Zero Emissions (NZE) Scenario outlines a pathway for the global energy sector to reach net zero CO₂ emissions by 2050 [2], underscoring the urgency of a decentralized, renewable-based energy system. Faced with growing environmental challenges and stringent regulations, the need for innovative energy storage and transportation solutions has become increasingly clear [3,4]. A major obstacle in this transition is the intermittent nature of renewable energy sources like solar and wind power [5]. Moreover, most efficient renewable energy production sites are often far from consumption points, making the development of technologies for long-term energy storage and long-distance energy transportation a priority [6]. Hydrogen (H₂) has emerged as a key energy vector, offering the flexibility needed to integrate renewable energy into a more balanced system between generation and demand [7]. In fact, the European Hydrogen Strategy (2020) has recognized the role of H₂ as a crucial element in achieving carbon neutrality by 2050 [8].

H₂ offers exceptional energy characteristics, including a high gravimetric energy density (120.1 MJ/kg), more than double that of conventional fuels [9], and zero direct CO₂ emissions during utilization [10,11]. Despite these advantages, approximately 96 % of global H₂ production remains fossil-based (“grey H₂”), primarily through steam methane reforming (SMR) and coal gasification [12]. These conventional methods are economically viable (0.7 to 4.9 €/kg H₂ [13,14]), but carry significant carbon footprints, creating an urgent need for cleaner alternatives [15]. Renewable-powered “green H₂” via water electrolysis provides a sustainable solution that simultaneously addresses multiple challenges: it produces high-purity H₂ with oxygen as the only by-product, serves as energy storage for intermittent renewables, and is particularly crucial for decarbonizing hard-to-electrify sectors [16–18]. Its operational simplicity, environmental benefits, and scalability are rapidly gaining attention, positioning it as a key technology for large-scale H₂ production [19,20].

To accelerate the green H₂ transition, the European Commission has established dual 2030 targets: 10 million tons each for domestic renewable H₂ production and imports [21]. Despite global H₂ demand reaching 97 Mt. in 2023, green H₂ represented less than 1 % of supply [14], highlighting a critical implementation gap. While projections show low-emission H₂ production could grow fifty-fold to 49 Mt. by 2030—with Europe potentially contributing 25 % (~12 Mt) of this total—significant barriers remain. Current green H₂ production costs (up to ~10.3 €/kg H₂ [14]) with significant regional disparities [22–27], underscore that the viability depends not only on technological factors (electrolyzer capital expenditure and renewable inputs [12]), but also on location-specific factors such as renewable energy potential, policy frameworks, infrastructure availability and financing conditions [28,29].

Despite these hurdles, the outlook remains promising. Advances in electrolysis technology and declining renewable energy costs could reduce green H₂ prices to ~1.7 €/kg H₂ by 2030 through economies of scale, carbon pricing and improved operational efficiency [12,13]—potentially making it cost-competitive with grey H₂ in many regions, accelerating the transition to sustainable energy systems [13]. Meanwhile, emerging solar-driven photocatalytic technologies using materials like metal nitrides (e.g., TiN, g-C₃N₄) and TiO₂-based nanostructures could complement large-scale electrolysis, particularly in high-irradiance regions [30,31].

One of the main challenges for large-scale H₂ implementation is the development of efficient, cost-effective, and safe storage and transportation technologies [32]. Its low volumetric energy density (0.01 MJ/L under room conditions) [33], and properties like low boiling point, high diffusivity and flammability, pose technical and safety concerns [34]. As a result, efforts are focused on developing advanced storage methods with the potential of getting energy density and the ability to address these issues. Among different H₂ storage and transport technologies, liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHCs) have recently emerged as a promising alternative to other methods such as compressed gas hydrogen (CGH₂), liquefied hydrogen (LH₂) or liquid ammonia (LNH₃) due to several distinctive advantages [35,36]. LOHCs allow for minimal H₂ loss long-term storage with high energy density [37–39]. They can store H₂ in a liquid state at ambient temperature and pressure, simplifying the storage and making them compatible with existing fossil fuel infrastructure network [36,38,40]. In terms of safety and handling, LOHCs show lower toxicity than other alternatives like NH₃ and are non-explosive and stable under normal conditions [41,42]. In addition, LOHCs have been shown to be 50 % and 25 % more cost-effective than CGH₂ and LH₂ [40].

LOHCs systems are based on a reversible chemical reaction that can store H₂ through many cycles. First, H₂ is stored by converting a H₂-lean molecule into a H₂-rich molecule via an exothermic, heterogeneous catalytic hydrogenation reaction, and it is then released via an endothermic, catalytic dehydrogenation reaction in the destination place [43,44]. The first research studies on LOHC H₂ storage were initiated in the early 1980s, focusing on the toluene/methylcyclohexane (TOL/MCH) system [36]. Following the research of the above system, numerous LOHC concepts based on different criteria have been evaluated. The system dibenzyltoluene/perhydro-dibenzyltoluene (H0-DBT/H18-DBT) is noted for its many favorable properties and it has been extensively studied in literature. The H₂-lean compound H0-DBT has been used in industry since the 1960s as a heat transfer oil and is therefore available in technical quantities at reasonable costs [45]. Even though the system benzyltoluene/perhydro-benzyltoluene (H0-BT/H12-BT) has also been mentioned in literature as a heat transfer oil, it has not been studied further. This system has a significantly lower viscosity than H0-DBT/H18-DBT, enabling its transportation and storage at lower temperatures [45]. Moreover, it offers a higher volumetric energy density, reduced flammability and lower toxicity than TOL/MCH [46] (see Table A. 1).

While H₂ offers significant environmental advantages, a comprehensive assessment of the entire value chain is essential for evaluating its sustainability. This requires a holistic and interconnected examination of H₂ production, transportation, storage, distribution and end-use. Such

an approach is crucial for guiding the development and deployment of H₂ technologies, maximizing economic efficiency, minimizing environmental impact and supporting the global transition towards a sustainable energy future. The life cycle assessment (LCA) methodology provides a robust framework for identifying and quantifying the environmental impacts associated with these processes. In the last two years, more than 100 papers have been published covering the LCA study of H₂ production. Research dedicated to the analysis of H₂ supply chains and the comparison among different technologies focuses more on the techno-economic aspect, and those studies dedicated to the environmental aspect offer quite different results, depending on the studied scenario. Wulf et al. [47] performed a LCA that compared the transportation of H₂ via trailer and pipeline in the form of CGH₂ and LOHC (H0-DBT/H18-DBT), finding that pipeline transportation of CGH₂ is the best option from the environmental point of view. Wulf & Zapp [48] conducted a LCA and a life cycle costing (LCC) comparing LH₂ and LOHC (TOL/MCH and H0-DBT/H18-DBT) technologies. The results showed that LH₂ is favorable from an environmental point of view, while LOHCs are favorable from an economic point of view. Bano et al. [49] compared the total environmental footprint of the transportation of H₂ in the form of LOHC (TOL/MCH) and CGH₂, pointing that the efficiency of the dehydrogenation step in the LOHC system is crucial to gain environmental advantage over CGH₂. Akhtar et al. [50] presented a LCA for H₂ delivery in the form of CGH₂ via tube trailers, and in the form of LH₂, LOHC (H0-DBT/H18-DBT) and LNH₃ via truck. The results showed that the transportation of CGH₂ via tube trailers is the most responsible candidate for short distances, whereas LOHC showed the worst results. Kanz et al. [51] studied the global warming potential (GWP) of the transportation of LH₂ from Africa to Germany by ship, and the distribution of CGH₂ by pipeline. Lee et al. [52] performed a comparative techno-economic and environmental assessment of large-scale overseas H₂ transportation via LH₂, LNH₃, TOL/MCH, H0-DBT/H18-DBT and methanol. The results showed that TOL/MCH was the most cost-effective and environmentally friendly technology, followed by LNH₃. Dickson et al. [53] presented a comparative economic and environmental sustainability analysis of LH₂, LNH₃, synthetic natural gas and three LOHC systems: methanol, H0-DBT/H18-DBT and TOL/MCH. The results indicate that, by 2050, LH₂ will be a promising carrier in economic and environmental terms. Noh et al. [44] analyzed the environmental impact and the energy efficiency of offshore H₂ supply chains utilizing CGH₂, LH₂, LOHC (TOL/MCH) and LNH₃. The results indicated that sea transportation has the highest environmental load for distances greater than 3000 km. For shorter distances, electricity consumption is the factor with the highest load. The environmental impact is lower when electricity source is completely renewable (wind). Prior studies have mainly focused on more conventional LOHC systems (methanol, TOL/MCH, H0-DBT/H18-DBT) or compared their techno-economic performance, but few have provided a comprehensive environmental assessment, particularly for the H0-BT/H12-BT system.

This study provides a comprehensive environmental assessment of the H₂ supply chain using the LOHC system H0-BT/H12-BT, identifying its key environmental impact points for the first time, and comparing it with conventional H₂ carriers (CGH₂, LH₂ and LNH₃) over both long and short transport distances. The analysis evaluates the potential of LOHC as a flexible and scalable alternative by benchmarking it against established H₂ technologies, including maritime transport as CGH₂, LH₂ and LNH₃ and land distribution via CGH₂, the dominant commercial method. Sensitivity analyses further explore optimization opportunities, while the integration of environmental and economic perspectives offers new insights into the feasibility and sustainability of the H0-BT/H12-BT system for large-scale H₂ storage and transport. Ten scenarios are defined, incorporating H₂ sea transportation and land distribution across Europe to assess the impact of different H₂ methods.

Although LNH₃ is not traditionally classified as a conventional H₂ storage technology like CGH₂ or LH₂, it was considered in this study due to its well-established industrial use, extensive transport infrastructure

and growing role as a hydrogen carrier. As one of the largest global H₂ consumers, its extensive handling experience and mature logistics make it a relevant comparator for assessing H₂ storage and transport technologies [54–57]. However, ammonia cracking, especially on a large-scale, remains challenging due to high temperature requirements and high energy demand. Advances in efficiency and catalyst design are needed for its wider adoption as a hydrogen supply route [58,59].

Given the challenges associated with LH₂ transport by truck (including high infrastructure complexity, boil-off losses and operational costs [32,60,61]) this study does not consider LH₂ for land distribution, prioritizing instead CGH₂, which remains the most widely used and commercially viable option. LH₂ is only assessed for maritime transport, where it has growing practical applications.

2. Methodology

2.1. Scenarios definition

The H₂ supply chains under consideration in this study consist of delivering renewable H₂ from a production site in southern Europe, the port of Algeciras (Spain), to an industrial site in northern Europe, the port of Rotterdam (The Netherlands). These locations were selected based on their potential for renewable H₂ production and consumption, respectively. In fact, the port of Rotterdam has been positioned as a future hub for green H₂ and new electricity storage forms [62]. In the port of Algeciras, H₂ is assumed to be produced by water electrolysis. Ten different H₂ supply scenarios divided into two steps are considered. First, H₂ is transported from the port of Algeciras to the port of Rotterdam by ship, in the form of LOHC, LH₂, CGH₂ or LNH₃. Then, H₂ is distributed from the port of Rotterdam to four cities located at different distances (Brussels, Cologne, Frankfurt and Vienna) by pipeline or truck, in the form of LOHC or CGH₂. The cities were chosen based on the distance from the port of Rotterdam to assess its effect. One of the key advantages of LOHCs is their compatibility with existing liquid fuel infrastructure, including pipelines, tankers and storage facilities, minimizing the need for new infrastructure investments [35]. The viscosity (4.3 and 6.6 mPa·s at 20 °C) and density (996 and 876 kg/m³ at 20 °C) of H0-BT and H12-BT are within the range of diesel (6.5 mPa·s and 850 kg/m³ at 20 °C) [63], enabling their transport through pipelines with minimal modifications [46,64,65]. Additionally, their similar hazard profiles enable the use of standard handling and safety protocols, making LOHCs a cost-effective and scalable solution for hydrogen logistics [65]. Land distribution using LH₂ or LNH₃ was excluded due to significant technical and safety challenges. LH₂ requires cryogenic tanks to maintain extremely low temperatures, and even small fluctuations can lead to H₂ boil-off, making it unsuitable for short and frequent transport cycles typical of overland transport [66–68]. The toxic and corrosive nature of LNH₃ requires specialized containment systems to prevent leakage during handling and transportation. It is more suitable for industrial applications or maritime transport, where large, centralized facilities can manage its risks and complexities more effectively [57,69].

Based on these considerations, the ten scenarios were defined as follows:

- Scenario 1: LOHC-1. H₂ is transported by ship (oil tanker) in the form of hydrogenated LOHC (H12-BT) from the port of Algeciras to the port of Rotterdam. Then, the LOHC is distributed to the destination cities by tanker truck, where it is dehydrogenated, and H₂ is consumed. The dehydrogenated LOHC (H0-BT) returns by tanker truck to the port of Rotterdam, and by ship (oil tanker) to the port of Algeciras to start again the cycle.
- Scenario 2: LOHC-2. The same as the scenario LOHC-1 but using oil pipeline instead of truck for the land distribution.
- Scenario 3: LOHC-3. H₂ is transported by ship (oil tanker) in the form of hydrogenated LOHC (H12-BT) from the port of Algeciras to the

port of Rotterdam, where it is dehydrogenated. Then, H₂ is compressed into cylindrical reinforced tanks (Type IV vessels) [60,70] under 700 bar clustered in Multi-Element Gas Containers (MEGCs) and distributed to the destination cities by truck in the form of CGH₂. The dehydrogenated LOHC (H0-BT) returns by ship (oil tanker) from the port of Rotterdam to the port of Algeciras to start again the cycle.

- Scenario 4: LOHC-4. The same as the scenario LOHC-3 but using pipeline instead of truck in the land distribution.
- Scenario 5: LH2-1. H₂ is liquefied and transported by ship in the form of LGH₂ from the port of Algeciras to the port of Rotterdam. Then, H₂ is re-gasified and compressed in Type IV vessels under 700 bar clustered in MEGCs and distributed to the destination cities by truck in the form of CGH₂.
- Scenario 6: LH2-2. The same as the scenario LH2-1 but using pipeline instead of trucks for the land distribution.
- Scenario 7: CGH2-1. H₂ is compressed in Type IV vessels under 700 bar and transported by container ship in the form of CGH₂ from the port of Algeciras to the port of Rotterdam. Currently, some prototypes with large CGH₂ transport vessels exist, but there are no large-scale commercial CGH₂ ships. Therefore, it was considered that CGH₂ transportation is carried out by means of Multi Element Gas Containers (MEGCs) with Type IV vessels under 700 bar. Given the hermetic nature of Type IV vessels and their ability to maintain high-pressure storage with minimal losses, the boil-off rate for CGH₂ during sea transportation was assumed to be negligible [60,70]. Then, H₂ is distributed to the destination cities by truck in MEGCs.
- Scenario 8: CGH2-2. The same as the scenario CGH2-1 but using pipelines instead of truck for the land distribution.
- Scenario 9: LNH3-1. H₂ is transported by ship in the form of LNH₃ from the port of Algeciras to the port of Rotterdam, where LNH₃ is cracked, and H₂ is released. Then, H₂ is compressed in Type IV vessels under 700 bar clustered in MEGCs and distributed to the destination cities by truck in the form of CGH₂.
- Scenario 10: LNH3-2. The same as the scenario LNH3-1 but using pipelines instead of trucks for land distribution.

This study focuses on H₂ delivery, covering conditioning, transport and post-processing steps. While H₂ production is outside the scope, it is assumed to be the same for all technologies, originating from water electrolysis and therefore classified as “green H₂” [71]. The assumption of green H₂ directly impacts the synthesis of ammonia, as conventional processes typically rely on H₂ derived from fossil fuels. By considering green H₂ as the feedstock, this study evaluates the environmental impacts of “green ammonia” production, reflecting a pathway that significantly reduces carbon emissions compared to traditional Haber-Bosch process [56,72,73].

Table 1 presents the properties of the H₂ technologies considered in this study, along with key parameters and process conditions of the supply chains. Each scenario assumes a supply of 150 tons of H₂ per day (tpd), i.e. 30 tpd to each destination city, with plants operating 8200 h per year. Ship capacities were based on standard options available in the database used (see Section 2.2.2). For LOHC, a tanker was considered; for CGH₂, a container ship, while for LH₂ and LNH₃, a liquefied natural gas tanker adapted for each carrier were considered. Based on plant and ship capacities, between 8 and 18 trips per year are sufficient for LOHC, LH₂ and LNH₃, making these scenarios realistic. However, CGH₂ requires more frequent trips due to the lower H₂ transport capacity of the ship. For land distribution, tanker trucks carrying hydrogenated LOHC to the destination city and returning dehydrogenated LOHC back to the port of Rotterdam were considered. For CGH₂, articulated trucks transporting MEGCs used for sea transportation were used. The H₂ capacity CGH₂ trucks is lower than that of LOHC, therefore a larger fleet to transport the same amount of H₂ is required in the latter case. It was assumed that trucks circulate continuously and that there are multiple drivers. As a result, the number of trucks required to meet daily H₂ demand varies for each destination; the greater the distance, the greater

Table 1

Properties, key parameters and process conditions considered in the study for the different H₂ storage and transportation technologies [32,44,46,51,52,65,68,74–86].

	LOHC (H0-BT/ H12-BT)	CGH ₂	LH ₂	LNH ₃
Properties				
Density (kg/m ³)	996/876 (20 °C)	40 (700 bar, 25 °C)	70.6 (−253 °C)	682 (−33 °C)
Boiling point at atm. (°C)	277–290/ 264–273	−253	−253	−33
Gravimetric H ₂ density (wt%)	6.2	100	100	17.8
Volumetric H ₂ density (kg H ₂ / m ³)	54.3	40	70.6	121.4
Conditioning				
Temperature (°C)	180	25	−253	450–500
Pressure (bar)	40	700	1	150
Electricity (kWh/kg H ₂)	0.50	2.67	6.76	0.81 kWh/kg NH ₃
Heat (kWh/kg H ₂)	−8.70	–	–	−4.50 kWh/ kg NH ₃
Post-processing^a				
Temperature (°C)	265–285	25	25	900
Pressure (bar)	1.5	700	700	40
Electricity (kWh/kg H ₂)	2.60 ^a / 4.25 ^b	0.7 ^a / 2.87 ^b	1.00 ^a / 3.30 ^b	6.43 / 6.54 kWh/kg NH ₃
Heat (kWh/kg H ₂)	11.00	–	–	–
Storage				
Temperature (°C)	25	25	−253	−33
Pressure (bar)	1	700	1.2	1
Sea transportation (ship)				
Capacity (DWT)	72,000	43,000	23,000	53,000
H ₂ capacity (t)	3795	975	2895	7545
Temperature (°C)	25	25	−253	−33
Pressure (bar)	1	700	1.2	1
Round trip distance (km)	4970	4970	4970	4970
Average speed (km/h)	35	35	35	35
Material loss rate or boil-off	0.1 %/voyage	0.0 %/d	0.2 %/d	0.04 %/d
Land distribution (truck)				
H ₂ capacity (t)	1.600	1.300	–	–
Temperature (°C)	25	25	–	–
Pressure (bar)	1	700	–	–
Average speed (km/h)	65	65	–	–
Land distribution (pipeline)				
Pressure (bar)	10–70	70	–	–
Electricity (kWh/kg H ₂ /km)	0.45 (round trip)	1.83	–	–

^a The post-processing step includes not only the specific treatment processes (dehydrogenation for LOHC, regasification for LH₂ and cracking for LNH₃), but also the compression of H₂ to the designated pressure required for its subsequent distribution via pipeline or truck, as indicated in the table.

^b Including the compression up to 100 bar (pipeline) and ^b including compression up to 700 bar (truck).

the fleet.

Catalysis plays a key role in the efficiency of hydrogenation and dehydrogenation reactions in LOHC systems [4]. Currently, platinum group metals (PGMs), especially platinum (Pt), are commonly used for their effectiveness [87]. However, due to their high cost, limited

availability and environmental impact, research is focusing on alternatives. Bimetallic catalysts that incorporate non-precious metals are being explored to create efficient solutions while reducing dependence on expensive and scarce materials [88]. For the evaluation of the hydrogenation and dehydrogenation processes, novel catalysts with low PGM content were considered: Pt-Ni/ γ -Al₂O₃ (0.5 wt% Pt, 25.0 wt% Ni) [89] and Pt-S/ γ -Al₂O₃ (0.30 wt% Pt, 0.05 wt% S) [90]. The productivity of these catalysts, 0.70 and 0.26 g H₂/g PGM/min, respectively, was determined under laboratory conditions, and it was used to calculate the required catalyst amount to meet the daily H₂ capacity, considering a catalyst's lifetime of two years for both.

2.2. Life cycle assessment

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a methodology used to evaluate the environmental aspects and potential impacts of a product, process, or service throughout its entire life cycle, from raw material extraction and manufacturing to distribution, use, and final disposal. This study follows the framework outlined in ISO 14040:2006 [91] and ISO 14044:2006 [92], dividing the LCA process into four key phases: goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment, and interpretation.

2.2.1. Goal and scope definition

The goal of the study is to quantify and compare the environmental impacts of the H₂ supply chain based on the LOHC system H0-BT/H12-BT and other H₂ technologies (CGH₂, LH₂ and LNH₃). The functional unit (FU) considered is defined as the delivery of 1 kg of H₂ (purity 99.9 % vol., 30 bar) destined for industry. The system boundaries include H₂ conditioning (hydrogenation, compression, liquefaction, NH₃ production, and subsequent storage), sea transportation, post-processing (dehydrogenation, compression, regasification, cracking and the previous storage) and land distribution (Fig. 1). Both the H₂ production and H₂ end-use phases have not been taken into account, since the study is focused on H₂ transportation methods, and these phases are assumed to be the same for all scenarios. The geographical scope is considered to be Europe.

2.2.2. Life cycle inventory (LCI)

The data used to complete the material and energy balance of the H₂ supply chains presented in the ten scenarios were obtained from various sources. For LOHC technology, the foreground data for hydrogenation and dehydrogenation processes were directly collected from experimental own sources. Data for sea transportation and land distribution were extracted and calculated from the literature. For the other technologies, data were similarly sourced from literature. **Appendix A** provides detailed inventories of the processes involved in the different H₂ storage and transportation technologies analyzed. The different supply chains were modelled with openLCA 2.0 software along with Ecoinvent v3.9.1 database, linking material and energy requirements to the background system processes of the database.

2.2.3. Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA)

The life cycle inventory assessment (LCIA) method used was EF v3.1, which has been formulated by the European Commission for application within the framework of the Environmental Footprint (EF) initiative [93]. The EF v3.1 method includes 16 impact categories groups: "Acidification", "Climate change", "Ecotoxicity, freshwater", "Eutrophication, freshwater", "Eutrophication, marine", "Eutrophication, terrestrial", "Human toxicity, cancer", "Human toxicity, non-cancer", "Ionizing radiation", "Land use", "Ozone depletion", "Particulate matter", "Photochemical ozone formation", "Resource use, fossils", "Resource use, minerals and metals" and "Water use" (see Table 2 to see the corresponding indicators and units).

For this study, midpoint and endpoint indicators were calculated. Midpoint indicators focus on specific environmental aspects and give detailed insights into the various impact categories, while endpoint indicators consolidate these impacts into a single, overall score for easier interpretation [94]. However, while endpoint indicators simplify the results, they also introduce uncertainty by compressing complex environmental data. Thus, both midpoint and endpoint results are examined to ensure a balanced and thorough understanding of the overall environmental impacts of each scenario.

Following the established methodology, the life cycle inventory data (inputs and outputs) were aggregated into the 16 midpoint-

Fig. 1. System boundaries of the H₂ supply chains concepts for the proposed scenarios.

Table 2
EF v3.1 impact categories with their indicator and unit [95].

Impact category	Indicator	Unit
Acidification	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	mol H ⁺ eq.
Climate change	Global Warming Potential (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq.
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems (CTU _e)	CTU _e
Eutrophication, freshwater	Fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (P)	kg P eq.
Eutrophication, marine	Fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N)	kg N eq.
Eutrophication, terrestrial	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	mol N eq.
Human toxicity, carcinogenic	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTU _h)	CTU _h
Human toxicity, non-carcinogenic	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTU _h)	CTU _h
Ionizing radiation (human health)	Human exposure efficiency relative to U ²³⁵	kBq U ²³⁵ eq.
Land use	Soil quality index	dimensionless
Ozone depletion	Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq.
Particulate matter	Human health effects associated with exposure to PM _{2.5}	disease incidence
Photochemical ozone formation	Tropospheric ozone concentration increase	kg NMVOC eq.
Resource use, fossils	Abiotic resource depletion – fossil fuels (ADP-fossil)	MJ, net calorific value
Resource use, minerals and metals	Abiotic resource depletion (ADP ultimate reserves)	kg Sb eq.
Water use	User deprivation potential (deprivation-weighted water consumption)	m ³ world eq. deprived

characterized impact categories listed above. These categories were then normalized, dividing their value by the overall inventory of a reference unit (e.g., the entire world) to express them as relative contributions of the impacts of the analyzed system. Subsequently, each impact category was multiplied by a weighting factor to reflect its relative importance based on established assessment criteria. Finally, the weighted impact categories were summed to derive a single overall EF endpoint score [95].

2.3. Economic assessment

The economic assessment aims to evaluate the economic viability of the H₂ supply across the same ten scenarios analyzed previously in the environmental assessment with the same system boundaries, in order to ensure consistency in the comparison of the different H₂ logistics concepts. Thus, the steps considered include the conditioning and subsequent transport of H₂ by ship from the port of Algeciras to the port of Rotterdam (in the form of LOHC, LH₂, CGH₂ or LNH₃), the distribution by land to four destination cities by pipeline or truck (in the form of LOHC or CGH₂) and the post-processing step. The H₂ production step is excluded from the analysis because it is considered to be the same for all scenarios (production by electrolysis). The scope includes a detailed cost analysis, focusing on both capital expenditure (CAPEX) and operational expenditure (OPEX) for each scenario. By comparing these costs, the goal is to identify the most cost-effective and sustainable options for H₂ storage and transportation technologies. A 25-year operational period is used as the basis for annualizing the related costs. This timeframe ensures that the costs are evaluated on a consistent long-term scale, accounting for the different processes and plant configurations across the various scenarios analyzed. The plants operate annually 8200 h, with a processing capacity of 150 tons of H₂ per day (51,250 tons of H₂ per year). The costs associated with catalyst replacement, including material costs, frequency of replacement and catalyst productivity, have been considered and incorporated into the OPEX for plants where they are used.

The levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH) was used as an indicator. It was calculated by dividing the annualized total expenditure (TOTEX) costs by the annual H₂ supply (Eq. 1). The annual TOTEX was calculated by summing the annual CAPEX and OPEX of the different processes (Eq. 2).

$$LCOH \left(\frac{\text{€}}{\text{kg H}_2} \right) = \frac{TOTEX \left(\frac{\text{€}}{\text{year}} \right)}{\text{annual hydrogen delivery} \left(\frac{\text{kg H}_2}{\text{year}} \right)} \quad (1)$$

$$TOTEX \left(\frac{\text{M€}}{\text{year}} \right) = \text{annualized CAPEX} \left(\frac{\text{M€}}{\text{year}} \right) + OPEX \left(\frac{\text{M€}}{\text{year}} \right) \quad (2)$$

The data needed for the economic evaluation come from different sources. Appendix B contains a detailed description of the methodology, data, references, considerations and assumptions used. The cost data found in the literature was scaled to match the plant and equipment capacities used in the analyzed scenarios. For this purpose, the Eq. 3 was used, which calculates the cost of the equipment with the required attribute (C_a) of size A_a , knowing the cost of the equipment with the base attribute (C_b) of size A_b . The cost exponent (n) was taken as 0.6 for all equipment except for compressors, which was assumed to be 0.85 [96].

$$\frac{C_a}{C_b} = \left(\frac{A_a}{A_b} \right)^n \quad (3)$$

Chemical engineering plant cost index (CEPCI) values were used to take into account the inflation over time. Equipment costs in the reference year (2024) were calculated from known costs in a base year (C_x) using Eq. 4.

$$C_{ref\ year} = C_{base\ year} \cdot \left(\frac{CEPCI_{ref\ year}}{CEPCI_{base\ year}} \right) \quad (4)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Environmental assessment

This section analyzes the results of the environmental impact assessment. “Climate change” category is first examined individually due to its importance. Next, the other major impact categories are presented collectively. Finally, the endpoint results are shown.

3.1.1. Global warming potential (GWP)

The initial focus is on the “Climate change” impact category, evaluated using the Global warming potential (GWP) index. This category is chosen for its simplicity and effectiveness in enabling comparisons with similar studies, and it requires a thorough analysis due to its critical importance meeting the requirements of legally binding international agreements. Fig. 2 compares the GWP per 1 kg of H₂ delivered across the four LOHC scenarios (LOHC-1 to LOHC-4). The analysis is broken down by cities and the different steps of the supply chain, including hydrogenation (conditioning), sea transportation, dehydrogenation (post-processing), distribution by truck or pipeline (land distribution). A notable observation is the significant contribution of the dehydrogenation process to GWP across all scenarios, it reaches 2.81 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂. This step accounts for a substantial portion of the total emissions (27.59 %–65.07 % depending on the scenario and the final destination city), underlining its energy-intensive nature. It requires considerable heat input provided by the combustion of natural gas, which emits CO₂ and contributes greatly to the GWP. In addition, the consumption of electricity, which is partly of fossil origin, further raises the CO₂ footprint. Land transportation by trucks, LOHC-1 and LOHC-3, shows considerably higher GWP values compared to LOHC-2 and LOHC-4, which use pipelines. Trucks rely on diesel, and frequent trips due to limited H₂ storage capacity result in high cumulative CO₂ emissions. The GWP of distribution by truck as CGH₂ (LOHC-3) is higher than the

Fig. 2. GWP per 1 kg of H₂ delivered to the different cities in the LOHC scenarios.

distribution as LOHC (LOHC-1), because the H₂ transport capacity of the former is lower. As a result, more trips and trucks are required to fulfill the same daily H₂ demand. Additionally, greater distances between cities lead to increase GWP. The values in LOHC-1 scenario up to Brussels (150 km), Cologne (250 km), Frankfurt (450 km) and Vienna (1150 km) are 0.47, 0.78, 1.41 and 3.60 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂, respectively (9.81–45.48 % of the total). Note that, in this case, there is a double-trip configuration (one-way trips to transport hydrogenated LOHC to the destination city and return trips to return dehydrogenated LOHC to the port of Rotterdam). In LOHC-3 scenario, the GWP values are 1.39, 1.83, 2.73 and 5.87 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂, respectively (24.30–57.61 %). Conversely, pipeline transportation, as seen in LOHC-2 and LOHC-4, reduces the GWP considerably, demonstrating that pipelines offer a more sustainable solution for large-scale H₂ distribution over land. In LOHC-4 case, where the distribution by pipeline is as CGH₂, the electricity consumption for H₂ compression is the most important contribution to the GWP. The values in LOHC-2, which is based on LOHC pipelines, up to Brussels (130 km), Cologne (225 km), Frankfurt (400 km) and Vienna (1045 km) are 0.06, 0.10, 0.18 and 0.46 kg CO₂ eq./kg

H₂, respectively (1.37–9.63 % of the total). As for LOHC trucks, go and return configuration was considered (one line to transport hydrogenated LOHC to the destination city and another line to return dehydrogenated LOHC to the port of Rotterdam). In LOHC-4, which is based on CGH₂ pipelines, the GWP values are 0.28, 0.36, 0.51 and 1.05 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂, respectively (6.17–19.55 %). The contributions of hydrogenation (0.85 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂) and sea transportation (0.66 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂) are relatively small but still notable (8.35–19.71 % and 6.45–15.21 %, respectively, depending on the scenario and the destination city). On the one hand, hydrogenation requires electricity and a Pt-based catalyst, whose synthesis process itself contributes indirectly to the GWP due to the emissions associated with Pt mining and refining. On the other hand, ships burn heavy fuel oil with high carbon contents and emit significant amounts of CO₂. Long sea routes further amplify this impact. While these steps contribute less to GWP compared to dehydrogenation and truck transportation, optimizing these processes remains essential for minimizing the environmental impact of the entire supply chain.

Fig. 3 presents the GWP per 1 kg of H₂ delivered for comparing the best LOHC scenario (LOHC-2) with the other technologies. The GWP contributions of hydrogen delivery technologies vary significantly across the different steps involved. The high GWP of the LH₂ scenarios (LH2-1 and LH2-2) is largely due to the conditioning (4.34 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂), as liquefaction of H₂ is an energy-intensive process, as well as storage before being transported by ship. LH₂ requires cryogenic tanks and refrigeration systems to maintain –253 °C, making its handling and infrastructure complex and with high energy consumption [60]. The post-processing step also carries considerable weight, including the processes of storage after ship transport, regasification and compression for H₂ to be distributed as CGH₂ (3.07 and 2.53 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂ in LH2-1 and LH2-2, respectively). Similarly, LNH₃ scenarios (LNH3-1 and LNH3-2) show high GWP contributions during post-processing (2.40 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂) due to the energy required for ammonia cracking, as well as during conditioning (1.53 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂) for ammonia synthesis. In the case of CGH₂ scenarios, the GWP of conditioning (0.91 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂) is minor and that of post-processing null. Contributions from sea transportation are generally not a dominant factor, except in the CGH₂ scenarios (CGH2-1 and CGH2-2), which exhibit a much higher GWP (1.77 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂). As with CGH₂ trucks, ships carrying CGH₂ on MEGCs have a much lower H₂ capacity than for the other technologies, requiring significantly more trips to meet the same demand. For the scenarios involving truck (LH2-1,

Fig. 3. GWP per 1 kg of H₂ delivered to the different cities in the best LOHC scenario and in the rest of hydrogen delivery scenarios.

CGH2-1, LNH3-1), the GWP for land distribution is significant, especially for Frankfurt and Vienna. This shows the inefficiency of distribution by truck for long distances, mirroring the trend seen in LOHC-based scenarios. In contrast, the use of pipelines in LOHC-2, LH2-2, CGH2-2, and LNH3-2 drastically reduces the GWP associated with land distribution, confirming that pipelines offer a more sustainable option for H₂ distribution. Overall, CGH-2 stands out as the most sustainable option due to its lower emissions from less energy-intensive conditioning and post-processing processes. However, its environmental efficiency diminishes in sea transportation due to the low ship H₂ carrying capacity. LOHC-2 follows, but its sustainability is hindered by the high emissions associated with the energy-intensive dehydrogenation process. In contrast, LH₂ and LNH₃ scenarios exhibit higher GWP, primarily due to the conditioning and post-processing requirements.

3.1.2. Other impact categories

To provide a more comprehensive understanding of the environmental consequences associated with different H₂ transport technologies and fully assess their sustainability, it is necessary to evaluate additional impact categories beyond GWP. The impact categories with the greatest weight in the overall impact, apart from GWP, are “Resource use, fossils”, “Acidification”, “Photochemical ozone formation”, “Resource use, minerals and metals” and “Particulate matter”. Fig. 4 shows the average significance of the different impact categories in the LOHC-based scenarios.

Fig. A. 1 in Appendix A compares the results of these four categories per 1 kg of H₂ delivered across the four LOHC scenarios (LOHC-1 to LOHC-4). As can be seen, these categories follow a similar trend to the GWP. In those scenarios where land distribution is by pipeline, the impact is lower. In addition, as the distance to the destination cities increases, the impact also increases. However, the importance of the different steps of the supply chain varies according to the impact category. For “Resource use, fossil”, as in the GWP, dehydrogenation emerges as the most impactful step due to the high consumption of natural gas to meet heat requirements, and due to the electricity consumption, where fossil sources prevail in the mix. Land distribution by truck also plays an important role in view of the large quantities of fuel required for the many trips over long distances. In the case of “Acidification”, hydrogenation contributes the most, mainly due to the Pt used in the catalyst, despite its low content. Mining and refining Pt involve energy-intensive processes, leading to substantial acidifying emissions, like sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and heavy metal pollution. Sea transportation also plays an important role in this category, since the heavy fuel oil used contains high levels of sulfur which imply the emission of SO₂ and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) into the atmosphere. Dehydrogenation is important due to the combustion of natural gas, which produces NO_x emissions, and the Pt of the catalyst. For “Photochemical ozone formation”, sea transport is by far the most significant contributor due to the use of

heavy fuel oil, which emits pollutants like NO_x and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) that lead to photochemical smog and therefore, ozone (O₃) production in the atmosphere. Dehydrogenation and hydrogenation also contribute to this impact category, though to a lesser extent, due to emissions from fuel and energy use. For “Resource use, minerals and metals”, the hydrogenation step stands out above the rest, followed by dehydrogenation, again due to the Pt used in the catalyst, which is a critical and valuable metal, and its extraction requires extensive mineral resources. The high impact associated with platinum derives from the depletion of valuable non-renewable mineral resources. Lastly, the distribution by truck is the largest contributor to “particulate matter” (PM_{2.5}) emissions (measured as “disease incidence”) due to fuel combustion, tire and brake wear, and road dust.

3.1.3. Endpoint

Fig. 5 compares the endpoint impact result per 1 kg of H₂ delivered across the four LOHC scenarios (LOHC-1 to LOHC-4). The trend is the same as for the GWP. Land distribution is the main driver of the differences in the final impacts of the LOHC scenarios, being greater when truck is used instead of pipeline. The greater the distance to cities, the greater the impact. LOHC-3 shows the highest overall environmental impact, especially for the most distant cities, indicating that its supply chain is less efficient and consumes more resources. LOHC-4 appears to offer a more balanced performance, with lower final impacts in most locations.

Fig. 5. Endpoint impact results per 1 kg of H₂ delivered to the different cities in the LOHC scenarios.

Fig. 4. Significance of the different impact categories in the LOHC scenarios.

Fig. 6 presents the endpoint impact results per 1 kg of H₂ delivered comparing the best LOHC scenario (LOHC-2) with the other technologies. Similarly to GWP, the use of pipeline infrastructure tends to mitigate endpoint impacts by reducing resource demand and distribution-related emissions compared to truck. Overall, CGH2-2 proves to be the most environmentally friendly option, followed by LOHC-2, which has higher emissions due to dehydrogenation. Sea transportation has a lower impact, though it significantly affects CGH2-1 and CGH2-2. LH₂ and LNH₃ scenarios show higher endpoint results, primarily due to differences in conditioning and post-processing complexity. While LH₂ regasification itself is not highly energy-intensive, its cryogenic storage requirements, continuous boil-off management, and handling challenges contribute significantly to its environmental impact. LNH₃, on the other hand, requires an energy-intensive cracking process but benefits from simpler storage conditions at moderate temperatures and pressures [60]. LOHC post-processing is dominated by the high-energy dehydrogenation step, which, despite its energy demand, avoids the infrastructure constraints and losses associated with LH₂ and LNH₃.

3.1.4. Sensitivity analysis

As previously discussed, dehydrogenation is a highly energy-intensive process requiring significant heat input, which contributes substantially to its environmental impact. One option to reduce this impact is the use of part of the dehydrogenated H₂ as a heat source. Therefore, in order to deliver the same amount of H₂, an extra amount of it must be transported along the whole supply chain. This section studies whether the impacts associated with such an extra H₂ transportation outweigh the expected benefits of the dehydrogenation step. The necessary amount of H₂ was calculated based on its heating value (120 MJ/kg [9]) and the heat requirements of the dehydrogenation process (11.0 kWh/kg H₂). This heat is considered to be provided by a H₂ burner with 90 % of efficiency and assuming 0.5 % of H₂ losses [79]. Calculations indicate that approximately 0.37 kg H₂ are required per kg H₂ released. However, to account for uncertainties such as operational inefficiencies or unforeseen losses, this requirement was conservatively increased to 0.40 kg H₂ per kg H₂ released. This consideration affects LOHC-1, LOHC-2, LOHC-3 and LOHC-4, introducing four new scenarios in the assessment: LOHC-1b, LOHC-2b, LOHC-3b and LOHC-4b. Fig. 7 compares the GWP per 1 kg of H₂ delivered of the original LOHC-based scenarios compared to the LOHC-based scenarios derived from the

sensitivity analysis.

To supply the same amount of H₂ at the point of consumption, 40.00 % more H₂ and therefore 40.00 % more LOHC must be transported. Thus, the GWP associated with hydrogenation and sea transportation steps increases by this percentage (from 0.85 to 1.19 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂, and from 0.66 to 0.92 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂, respectively). In contrast, the GWP associated with dehydrogenation is reduced by 70.12 % (from 2.81 to 0.84 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂). For land distribution, the GWP in scenarios LOHC-3b and LOHC-4b remains unchanged compared to LOHC-3 and LOHC-4 because dehydrogenation takes place directly at the port of Rotterdam, eliminating the need to transport the additional H₂ to the destination cities. Conversely, in LOHC-1b and LOHC-2b, the GWP increases compared to LOHC-1 and LOHC-2 because the additional H₂ must be transported to each city, where the dehydrogenation is performed locally. This added transport step increases emissions, impacting the overall GWP. Land distribution via pipeline remains the most sustainable option for H₂ delivery. In general, the overall GWP of LOHC-1b, LOHC-2b, LOHC-3b and LOHC-4b is lower than that of LOHC-1, LOHC-2, LOHC-3 and LOHC-4 for all cities, with the only exception being the distribution by truck to Vienna in LOHC-1b, which is the most distant city.

The endpoint results indicate notable shifts in environmental impacts (Fig. 8). As expected, the hydrogenation and sea transportation steps show a 40.00 % increase in impacts for the LOHC-1b, LOHC-2b, LOHC-3b and LOHC-4b scenarios compared to LOHC-1, LOHC-2, LOHC-3 and LOHC-4 (from 0.17 to 0.63 mPt/kg H₂, and from 0.09 to 0.12 mPt/kg H₂, respectively). Conversely, dehydrogenation impacts are 59.09 % lower in the updated scenarios (from 0.18 to 0.07 mPt/kg H₂), although this reduction is smaller than the 70.12 % decrease observed for GWP. Despite improvements in the dehydrogenation step, the overall environmental benefits are marginal. For LOHC-1 versus LOHC-1b, the endpoint remains nearly unchanged for Rotterdam, Brussels and Cologne, and slightly higher for Frankfurt and Vienna. Similarly, for LOHC-2 versus LOHC-2b, the endpoint is slightly lower in most cities, except in Vienna, where it remains almost the same. For LOHC-3 and LOHC-4 versus LOHC-3b and LOHC-4b, the endpoint is minimally lower for all cities. This shows that while using H₂ as a heat source reduces the impact of dehydrogenation, it does not significantly enhance the environmental performance of the entire supply chain, suggesting that alternative strategies need to be explored.

Fig. 6. Endpoint impact results for 1 kg of H₂ delivered to the different cities in the best LOHC scenario and in the rest of hydrogen delivery scenarios.

Fig. 7. GWP per 1 kg of H₂ delivered to the different cities in the sensitivity analysis of the LOHC scenarios.

Fig. 8. Endpoint impact results per 1 kg of H₂ delivered to the different cities in the sensitivity analysis of the LOHC scenarios.

3.2. Economic assessment

This section evaluates the economic viability of H₂ delivery through different transport methods, comparing LOHC, LH₂, CGH₂ and LNH₃ technologies. The analysis initially focuses on the ten baseline scenarios previously defined (see Section 2.1): LOHC-1, LOHC-2, LOHC-3, LOHC-4, LH₂-1, LH₂-2, CGH₂-1, CGH₂-2, LNH₃-1, and LNH₃-2. For each technology, the costs associated with the different steps of the H₂ supply chain are evaluated: conditioning, sea transportation, post-processing and land distribution for each technology are assessed (see Table 3 for the cost breakdown). The total costs for each scenario are then derived by applying the cost values from the table to each step and technology, with the resulting values presented in Fig. 9. These costs encompass both CAPEX for infrastructure and OPEX for ongoing operations.

For LOHC-based scenarios, the main cost drivers are dehydrogenation (post-processing) and land distribution. The energy-intensive dehydrogenation step contributes significantly to overall costs,

Table 3

Costs breakdown by technology for 1 kg of H₂ delivered (€/kg H₂).

	LOHC (H0-BT/H12-BT)	LH ₂	CGH ₂	LNH ₃
Conditioning	0.25	0.99	0.23	0.32
Storage	0.16 ^a /0.15 ^b	0.39	0.91	0.26
Sea transportation	0.20	0.33	0.24	0.12
Post-processing	01.03 ^a /0.86 ^b	0.05	0.00	0.88

^a LOHC-1 and LOHC-2 configuration: with a dehydrogenation unit in each destination city (5 units in total). ^b LOHC-3 and LOHC-4 configuration: with a single dehydrogenation unit at the port of Rotterdam.

whereas hydrogenation (conditioning) incurs lower costs due to its lower energy demand. Storage costs are minimal since LOHC can be stored at ambient conditions in standard double-walled containers, similar to crude oil or diesel, without losses. Sea transportation remains

Fig. 9. Costs for 1 kg of H₂ delivered in different scenarios.

a cost-competitive step, reinforcing the viability of LOHC in large-scale logistics. Finally, distribution costs are highly dependent on the transportation method (see Fig. B.1). The total cost of land distribution accounts for transporting 1/5 kg of H₂ to each of the destination cities (excluding Rotterdam, where no further distribution occurs, as the H₂ is delivered directly to the port), resulting in a total of 1 kg of H₂.

In the reference setting of 150 tpd total delivery (30 tpd per destination city), LOHC truck distribution is the most economical option, followed by LOHC pipelines, CGH₂ trucks and CGH₂ pipelines, which present the highest costs. LOHC trucks (LOHC-1) benefit from a higher H₂ transport capacity per trip and operation at ambient pressure, eliminating the costs associated with high-pressure compression required for CGH₂ distribution. Fewer trips are needed, leading to lower fuel consumption and maintenance costs, making LOHC trucking the most cost-effective solution on this scale. LOHC pipelines (LOHC-2), while requiring a dual infrastructure (one line for hydrogenated LOHC and another for dehydrogenated LOHC), avoid costly compression systems incurring in low costs but slightly higher than LOHC trucks. In contrast, CGH₂-based distribution presents higher costs at this setting. CGH₂ trucks (LOHC-3) have lower H₂ transport capacity per trip compared to LOHC trucks, which results in a larger fleet size being required to meet demand, thereby increasing costs. Additionally, the storage of CGH₂ in Type IV vessels arranged in MEGCs must be accounted for, as each truck transports two MEGCs. The costs associated with this storage, which are part of the overall land distribution system, contribute further to the total expenses. Furthermore, the high-pressure storage and compression costs associated with CGH₂ also increase the overall expenses, making this option less economically favorable. The most expensive alternative is CGH₂ pipelines (LOHC-4), which require high-strength materials to withstand elevated pressures, along with energy-intensive compression stations to maintain operating conditions, and stringent safety and regulatory regulations. In the case of pipelines, both construction and operation costs are considered.

Infrastructure configuration also influences cost distribution across the supply chain. In LOHC-1 and LOHC-2, decentralized dehydrogenation facilities (each with a capacity of 30 tpd) are installed across the five destination cities, increasing capital and operational costs of post-processing due to multiple smaller units. Conversely, LOHC-3 and LOHC-4 centralize dehydrogenation at a single 150 tpd facility in the port of Rotterdam, reducing the costs of this step and infrastructure

duplication.

Among the alternatives, LH₂ exhibits the highest costs, primarily due to the energy-intensive liquefaction process (post-processing) and the strict thermal management requirements during storage and transport. Boil-off losses during shipping further increase the economic burden. In contrast, CGH₂ emerges as a cost-effective technology, benefiting from lower conditioning costs and minimal post-processing requirements, as compressed H₂ can be readily used without further transformation. However, storage in Type IV vessels arranged in MEGCs incurs significant costs, as a large number of units is required to meet demand, adding considerable expenses. LNH₃ scenarios present competitive sea transportation costs due to higher H₂ density of ammonia, but high post-processing costs associated with ammonia cracking, necessary to recover H₂ in a high-purity form, reduce its economic attractiveness. In terms of overall costs, CGH₂ scenarios are comparable to LOHC, reflecting the balance between its storage and distribution challenges, along with relatively lower conditioning and post-processing costs compared to LH₂ and LNH₃.

A sensitivity analysis evaluates the effect of repurposing existing natural gas pipelines for CGH₂ instead of constructing new infrastructure. This modification is applied to the LOHC-4, LH₂-2, CGH₂-2 and LNH₃-2 scenarios, introducing four additional cases: LOHC-4c, LH₂-2c, CGH₂-2c and LNH₃-2c. All other process parameters remain unchanged. For this analysis, pipeline refitting and operating costs were considered (see Table B. 3). The results indicate that land distribution costs in these new scenarios (LOHC-4c, LH₂-2c, CGH₂-2c and LNH₃-2c) are reduced by 84.36 % compared to their original counterparts (LOHC-4, LH₂-2, CGH₂-2 and LNH₃-2), significantly lowering total costs by 18.41 %, 16.36 %, 19.05 % and 17.35 %, respectively. The cost savings primarily stem from avoiding the high capital expenses of constructing the new infrastructure. However, adapting pipelines for CGH₂ entails additional costs due to hydrogen's properties, such as lower density, higher diffusivity and the issue of hydrogen embrittlement.

Fig. B.1 in Appendix B illustrates distribution costs as a function of distance for the set reference of 30 tpd per city. As expected, the distribution costs exhibit a linear increase with distance across all methods, reflecting the proportional scaling of operational expenses such as fuel consumption, maintenance, and compression requirements. LOHC truck distribution remains the most economical option, benefiting from high

H₂ transport capacity per trip and the absence of high-pressure compression requirements. In contrast, LOHC pipelines incur slightly higher costs but remain more economical than CGH₂-based options due to lower pressure requirements. The costs associated with CGH₂ truck distributions, although comparable to those of LOHC trucks and pipelines, should be considered in the context of the significant expenses related to the storage and transport of compressed H₂ in Type IV vessels and MEGCs. These additional storage costs notably impact on the overall economics of CGH₂ truck-based transport. Lastly, CGH₂ pipelines present the highest costs, primarily driven by high-pressure operation, energy-intensive compression process, and substantial infrastructure investment requirements.

Fig. 10 illustrates the impact of daily transport capacity (tpd) on H₂ distribution costs, expressed in €/kg H₂/km, emphasizing the importance of economies of scale. For capacities below 150 tpd, LOHC truck distribution is the most cost-effective option due to lower infrastructure requirements and greater operational flexibility, followed by LOHC pipeline distribution. LOHC trucks maintain a significant cost advantage over CGH₂ trucks, owing to their higher H₂ transport capacity, which reduces the number of required trips. Additionally, LOHC trucks avoid the significant cost associated with storing and transporting compressed H₂ in Type IV vessels arranged in MEGCs, which are required for CGH₂ truck distribution. Costs for both LOHC and CGH₂ trucks remain relatively constant across different capacities, as increased demand is met by expanding the truck fleet, leading to a linear increase in operational costs. As daily transport capacity increases, pipelines become the most economical alternative, particularly for CGH₂, where economies of scale significantly drive cost reductions. CGH₂ pipeline costs decline steeply at lower capacities and continue decreasing at a slower rate beyond 300 tpd, as high initial infrastructure costs are distributed over a larger transport volume. LOHC pipeline costs also decrease with increasing capacity, but at a more gradual pace due to their lower operational pressure and the absence of high-pressure compression needs. While LOHC pipelines benefit from economies of scale, their cost reduction trend stabilizes beyond 150 tpd, as liquid fuel pipelines are less sensitive to scale effects than high-pressure gas pipelines. The break-even point, at which pipeline transport becomes more cost-effective than truck-based distribution, is observed at approximately 125 tpd, reinforcing the suitability of pipelines for long-distance, high-volume H₂ transport.

Overall, the findings highlight the trade-off between scalability and flexibility in H₂ distribution strategies. LOHC truck distribution remains preferable for low-capacity and flexible distribution applications over CGH₂ truck distribution, whereas pipeline distribution is more cost-effective for large-scale and long-term infrastructure investments. CGH₂ pipelines exhibit substantial cost reductions with increasing

capacity, reinforcing their viability for large-volume hydrogen corridors, while LOHC pipelines present a more stable cost trend. However, repurposed CGH₂ pipelines emerge as the most economical land distribution option. The selection of a suitable distribution method should consider transport demand, infrastructure availability, and investment horizon to ensure economic feasibility.

In summary, LOHC remains viable alternative depending on regional infrastructure and technological advancements. Despite the cost challenges associated with dehydrogenation, LOHC technology offers long-term potential for cost reductions as advancements in catalyst efficiency and heat integration drive down both CAPEX and OPEX. This positions LOHC as a flexible and scalable hydrogen transport solution, particularly in cases where existing liquid fuel infrastructure can be leveraged.

4. Conclusions

This study provides a comprehensive environmental and economic assessment of H₂ delivery by means of H0-BT/H12-BT LOHC system, and compares it with CGH₂, LH₂ and LN₂H₃ systems. The results highlight that, while LOHC technology offers strong potential for future H₂ supply chains, several challenges must be addressed to enhance its competitiveness.

From an environmental perspective, dehydrogenation is the largest contributor to global warming potential (GWP) and other impact categories in LOHC scenarios, primarily due to its energy-intensive nature. Although the use of hydrogen as a heat source for dehydrogenation reduces GWP and endpoint by 70.12 % and 59.09 %, respectively, it increases the environmental burden in other steps of the supply chain (e.g., transportation and distribution), making this approach less effective overall. These results highlight the need for alternative strategies to optimize the environmental performance of the LOHC supply chain. Land distribution via pipeline consistently delivers lower environmental impacts compared to truck-based, particularly for long-distance destination cities and especially for LOHC pipelines instead of CGH₂ pipelines. LOHC trucks show lower impacts than CGH₂ trucks, owing to higher H₂ transport capacity per trip and ambient pressure operation. Overall, while CGH₂ emerges as the most environmentally friendly option due to the lower conditioning and post-processing demands, LOHC demonstrates its strengths, making it a viable option for long-distance H₂ transport in regions equipped with suitable infrastructure.

From an economic perspective, LOHC technology remains competitive despite the high operational costs of dehydrogenation. It demonstrates strong potential and benefits from relatively low sea transportation costs, which enhances its competitiveness in large-scale,

Fig. 10. Distribution costs of hydrogen delivery as a function of transport capacity, in tons of H₂ per day (tpd), depending on the transport method.

long-distance H₂ transport. While LH₂ and LNH₃ technologies face cost disadvantages due to energy-intensive liquefaction and cracking processes, respectively, CGH₂ offers greater cost efficiency overall, though its storage requirements entail significant expenses. The analysis highlights the critical role of distribution infrastructure in determining total delivery costs. For capacities below 150 tpd, LOHC truck-based distribution is the most economical option, leveraging flexibility, higher H₂ transport capacity per trip (compared to CGH₂ trucks) and no high-pressure storage requirements. LOHC pipelines operate at ambient conditions and can leverage existing liquid fossil fuel infrastructure, offering cost advantages over CGH₂ pipelines, which require energy-intensive compressor stations and high-strength materials. The sensitivity analysis shows that repurposing natural gas pipelines can reduce land distribution costs by up to 84.36 %, leading to total cost reductions of 18.41 %–19.05 %, depending on the scenario. Although truck-based systems require lower upfront investments, their efficiency declines over long distances due to increased trip frequency, leading to higher fuel and maintenance costs. As transport capacity increases, pipeline distribution becomes more cost-effective due to economies of scale.

The findings highlight the complexity of selecting an optimal H₂ transport method, with each technology offering distinct advantages and drawbacks across different steps of the supply chain. For sea transportation, LNH₃ stands out for its high hydrogen density (17.8 wt% versus 6.2 wt% for LOHC) and well-established infrastructure, though its toxicity and environmental risks hinder widespread use [97]. CGH₂, on the other hand, emerges as the most efficient and economical option for conditioning and post-processing due to its simplicity and low energy consumption, despite storage costs. For land distribution, LOHC pipelines offer the lowest environmental impact, while CGH₂ pipelines prove to be more cost-effective, particularly when repurposing existing infrastructure. In conclusion, LOHC technology shows strong potential as a scalable H₂ storage and transport solution, particularly in regions with repurposed fossil fuel infrastructure and large-scale maritime transport routes. Its low-cost sea transportation and compatibility with existing logistics networks enhance its feasibility. However, advancements in dehydrogenation technology are crucial to overcoming the primary environmental and economic challenges. Future research should focus on improving dehydrogenation efficiency, exploring alternative energy sources and enhancing the circularity of the LOHC supply chain, particularly catalysts used in hydrogenation and dehydrogenation. Efforts to optimize lifecycle efficiency and minimize resource consumption will be essential for maximizing the environmental benefits and long-term viability of this technology. With continued technological progress and supportive policy frameworks, LOHC could play a significant role in the global decarbonization efforts.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

I. Rey: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **V.L. Barrio:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **I. Agirre:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2025.126862>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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